

Quantum deformation and Quantum Entanglement.

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Abstract

Recent study suggests that there are natural connections between quantum entanglement and the quantum YangBaxter equation. The present paper introduce the unitary solutions of the Quantum Yang–Baxter Equation derived via the quantization-deformation of a Poisson Lie group associated to an r-matrix (solution of a classical Yang Baxter equation). The solution of the algebraic Quantum Yang Baxter equation that we explore contain a deformation parameter h , and will be used to performs quantum entanglement when acting on (multi)-qubit quantum states.

Keywords: *quantization-deformation , Quantum Yang Baxter equation, quantum entanglement.*

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1 Introduction

Quantum entanglement [1, 2, 3, 4] as a fundamental concept of distinguishing classical physics from quantum physics has become a widely exploited resource in quantum information and computation. The quantum entanglement plays key role in the quantum information and quantum computation theory [5] and has been widely exploited in quantum teleportation [6], quantum algorithms [7] and quantum cryptography [8, 9]. In view of these remarkable realizations and implementations, the concept of entanglement [10, 11, 12] is expected to have many other implications and applications in others areas of research, especially condensed matter physics.

L. Kauffman and S. Lomonaco have constructed topological quantum gate entangler for two-qubit state [13]. These topological operators are called braiding operators that can entangle quantum states. These operators are also unitary solution of quantum Yang-Baxter equation. The complex relationship among topological entanglement, quantum entanglement, and quantum computational universality has been explored in a series of papers [14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22].

There are natural relationships between quantum entanglement and topological entanglement [23]. One way to study topological entanglement and quantum entanglement is to try making direct correspondences between patterns of topological linking and entangled quantum states. One approach of this kind was initiated by Aravind [24], suggesting that observation of a link would be modelled by deleting one component of the link

Quantum gate entangler was also constructed for multi-qubit states based on a topological and geometrical method in [25]. In particular unitary operators that can entangle multi-qubit quantum states was constructed for the states satisfying the completely separability condition defined by the ideal of the Segre embedding. Quantum gates entanglers for different classes of multipartite states based on the definition of W and GHZ concurrence classes was developed in [27, 26].

In the other side, the development of the quantum inverse scattering method (QISM) [28] intended for investigations of integrable models of the quantum field theory and statistical physics gives rise to some interesting algebraic constructions. These investigations allow to select a special class of Hopf algebras [29] now known as quantum groups and quantum algebras [30, 31, 32, 34, 35].

The main reason that quantum groups are of such great importance is that they are closely related to the so called quantum Yang-Baxter equation[36], which plays a prominent role in many areas of research such as knot theory, solvable lattice models, conformal field theory, quantum integrable systems and quantum information.

Quantum groups are defined as a non abelian Hopf algebras [37]. A way to generate them consists of deforming the abelian algebra of smooth functions on the group. into a non abelian one (*-product),using the so called deformation quantization or star-quantization [38, 39, 40, 41]. A star-quantization method is used also to develop a theory of (topological) quantum groups in [43, 44, 42] and to realize a deformed Yangian algebra in [45].

There are many applications of quantum algebra in physics [46, 47]. A relationship between quantum groups and quantum entanglement can be found in references [48, 49]. In [48] was performed a possible connection between quantum groups, non-extensive statistical mechanics and entanglement through the entropic parameter q . The problem of separability in terms of compact quantum groups was addressed in [49]. Quantum algebras associated with maximally entangled states were investigated in [50, 51, 52]. Unitary solutions of the braided YBE (i.e., the braid group relation) as well as unitary solutions of the quantum Yang Baxter equation (QYBE) [53] was often identified with universal quantum gates.

The main objective of this work, is to show explicitly that the universal R -matrix (solution of the algebraic quantum Yang Baxter equation) obtained from the quantization-deformation of a Poisson Lie group can be considered as quantum gate which can performs topological entanglement when acting on quantum states.

This paper is organized as follows, the second section is devoted to a review of a basic definitions of the quantization-deformation of a Poisson Lie group associated to an r -matrix (solution of classical Yang Baxter equation) and to present the Drinfeld-Takhtajan approach to construct quantum algebras and to derive unitary solutions of the quantum Yang Baxter equation. Section 3 introduces quantum operators, solutions of the algebraic quantum Yang Baxter equation that can performs quantum entanglement of multi-qubit quantum states. In section 4 we will construct quantum gate entanglers from a star product on the Poisson Lie group $SL(2)$ and show that these quantum operators entangle states on a vector space considered as the space of representation of the Lie algebra $sl(2)$.

2 Quantization of Poisson Lie group:

Let G be a Lie group with Lie algebra g , we denote by (X_i) a basis of g and $U(g)$ the universal enveloping algebra of g . If $r \in \wedge^2 g$, we consider the elements r^{12}, r^{13}, r^{23} of $U(g) \otimes U(g) \otimes U(g)$ defined by:

$$\begin{aligned} r^{12} &= r^{ij} X_i \otimes X_j \otimes 1 \\ r^{13} &= r^{ij} X_i \otimes 1 \otimes X_j \\ r^{23} &= r^{ij} 1 \otimes X_i \otimes X_j \end{aligned}$$

where $r = r^{ij} X_i \otimes X_j$. We say that r satisfies the Classical Yang-Baxter Equation (CYBE) if:

$$[r^{12}, r^{13}] + [r^{12}, r^{23}] + [r^{13}, r^{23}] = 0 \tag{1}$$

Such an element is called a r -matrix. To each r , we associate a Poisson structure on G by putting:

$$\{\varphi, \psi\} = r^{ij} (X_i^\ell(\varphi) X_j^\ell(\psi) - X_i^r(\varphi) X_j^r(\psi)) \quad \varphi, \psi \in C^\infty(G) \tag{2}$$

where X_i^ℓ (resp. X_j^r) are the left-invariant (resp. right-invariant) vector fields on G corresponding to X_i (resp. X_j).

Definition 1 (Poisson Lie group)

A Poisson-Lie group is a Lie group G endowed with a Poisson structure $\{, \}$ associated to a r -matrix satisfying the CYBE.

The quantization-deformation of a Poisson-Lie group $(G, \{, \})$ is a deformation of the commutative algebra $C^\infty(G)$ which turns it to a new noncommutative algebra $C^\infty(G)[[h]]$, where h is a deformation parameter. We shall assume that $|h| < 1$. In the limit $h \rightarrow 0$, $C^\infty(G)[[h]]$ reduces to the commutative algebra $C^\infty(G)$. The algebra $C^\infty(G)[[h]]$ as a vector space coincides with $C^\infty(G)$, but has a new product $*$ called a star product.

Definition 2 (Star product)

A star product on a Poisson Lie Group G is a bilinear map:

$$\begin{aligned} * : C^\infty(G) \otimes C^\infty(G) &\longrightarrow C^\infty(G)[[h]] \\ \varphi * \psi &= \varphi \cdot \psi + \sum_{i=1} C_i(\varphi, \psi) h^i \end{aligned}$$

such that, for all $\varphi, \psi, \chi \in C^\infty(G)$:

- 1) C_i is a bidifferential operator on $C^\infty(G)$
- 2) $\varphi * 1 = 1 * \varphi = \varphi$
- 3) $C_1(\varphi, \psi) = \{\varphi, \psi\}$
- 4) $(\varphi * \psi) * \chi = \varphi * (\psi * \chi)$.

Since G is a group, there is a naturel comultiplication Δ on $C^\infty(G) \rightarrow C^\infty(G) \otimes C^\infty(G)$:

$$\Delta(\varphi)(x, y) = \varphi(xy) \quad (\varphi \in C^\infty(G), x, y \in G).$$

The problem of the quantization is to get a star-product on the group G such that the compatibility relation

$$\Delta(\phi * \psi) = (\Delta(\phi) * \Delta(\psi)) \tag{3}$$

is satisfied. where the star-product on the right side is canonically defined on $C^\infty(G) \otimes C^\infty(G)$ by

$$(\phi \otimes \psi) * (\phi' \otimes \psi') = (\phi * \phi') \otimes (\psi * \psi'). \tag{4}$$

The corresponding star product was built by V. Drinfeld and L. Takhtajan in a purely algebraic way. They first look for a formal element $F \in U(\mathfrak{g}) \otimes U(\mathfrak{g})[[\hbar]]$ given by $F = 1 + \sum_{i \geq 1} F_i \hbar^i$, ($F_i \in U(\mathfrak{g}) \otimes U(\mathfrak{g})$) such that the product:

$$\varphi * \psi = \mu((F^{-1})^r(F)^\ell(\varphi \otimes \psi)) \tag{5}$$

is a star product, (where μ is the usual multiplication on the algebra of smooth functions over the group G). The associativity axiom of the star product looks:

$$(\Delta_0 \otimes id)F.(F \otimes 1) = (1 \otimes \Delta_0)F.(1 \otimes F) \tag{6}$$

where Δ_0 is the coproduct of the enveloping algebra $U(\mathfrak{g})$.

Now if we introduce the following element given by Drinfeld [54]

$$R_F = F_{21}^{-1}.F \tag{7}$$

where $F_{21} = P.F_{12}.P$, (P is the twisting map given by $P : \mathfrak{g} \otimes \mathfrak{g} \rightarrow \mathfrak{g} \otimes \mathfrak{g}$).

Then we can easily show that R_F defines a quasitriangular structure on the quantized enveloping algebra $U(\mathfrak{g})[[\hbar]]$, given by:

$$(\Delta_F \otimes id)R_F = (R_F)_{13}.(R_F)_{23}.$$

$$(id \otimes \Delta_F)R_F = (R_F)_{13}.(R_F)_{12}.$$

where the coproduct Δ_F of the quantized enveloping algebra $U(\mathfrak{g})[[\hbar]]$ is given by $\Delta_F(X) = F^{-1}.\Delta_0(X).F$.

It is possible to show that the universal R-matrix R_F gratifies the algebraic quantum Yang-Baxter equation

$$(R_F)_{12}.(R_F)_{13}.(R_F)_{23} = (R_F)_{23}.(R_F)_{13}.(R_F)_{12}. \tag{8}$$

From the fact that $\phi * 1 = 1 * \phi = \phi$ for all $\phi \in C^\infty(G)$, we deduce that

$$(id \otimes \varepsilon)F = (\varepsilon \otimes id)F = 1; \tag{9}$$

consequently

$$(\varepsilon \otimes id)(R_F) = (id \otimes \varepsilon)(R_F) = 1. \tag{10}$$

From the definition(7) we deduce that

$$(R_F)_{21}.R_F = 1. \tag{11}$$

If we Consider now a finite dimensional vector space H and let ρ be a finite dimensional irreducible representation of the Lie algebra \mathfrak{g} on H , then the R -matrix $R = (\rho \otimes \rho)(R_F)$ taking values in $End_{\mathbb{C}}(H \otimes H)$ satisfies the algebraic quantum Yang-Baxter equation (QYBE)

$$R_{12}.R_{13}.R_{23} = R_{23}.R_{13}.R_{12}. \tag{12}$$

We assume that $\{e_0, e_1, \dots, e_{n-1}\}$ is a basis of H over the Field \mathbb{C} and we denote the basis of the tensorial product $H \otimes H$ as $\{e_i \otimes e_j / i, j \in \{0, 1, \dots, n-1\}\}$. Using this basis we may describe the operator R by its action on the generators of $(H \otimes H)$

$$R(e_i \otimes e_j) = R_{ij}^{kl}(e_k \otimes e_l)$$

The algebraic Yang Baxter equation(12)can be rewritten as :

$$R_{im}^{ab} \cdot R_{dn}^{ic} \cdot R_{ef}^{mn} = R_{mk}^{bc} \cdot R_{lf}^{ak} \cdot R_{de}^{lm}$$

and if we introduce the matrix $B = PR$, where P considered now as the permutation operator on the tensor vector space $H \otimes H$ with $P_{kl}^{ij} = \delta_l^i \delta_k^j$ then the matrix B satisfies the Braided quantum Yang Baxter Equation

$$B_{jm}^{bc} \cdot B_{dm}^{aj} \cdot B_{ef}^{mn} = B_{lj}^{ab} \cdot B_{mf}^{jc} \cdot B_{de}^{lm} \quad (13)$$

which can be rewritten in a compact form as

$$(B \otimes id) \cdot (id \otimes B) \cdot (B \otimes id) = (id \otimes B) \cdot (B \otimes id) \cdot (id \otimes B). \quad (14)$$

The braided Yang Baxter equation bears a close resemblance to the relation

$$\sigma_i \sigma_{i+1} \sigma_i = \sigma_{i+1} \sigma_i \sigma_{i+1}$$

of the Artin braid group defined by:

Definition 3 *The Artin braid group on n -strands is denoted by B_n and is generated by $\{\sigma_i | 1 \leq i \leq n-1\}$. The group B_n consists of all words of the form $\sigma_{j_1}^{\pm 1} \sigma_{j_2}^{\pm 1} \dots \sigma_{j_n}^{\pm 1}$ modulo the following relationships.*

$$\sigma_i \sigma_{i+1} \sigma_i = \sigma_{i+1} \sigma_i \sigma_{i+1} \text{ for all } 1 \leq i \leq n-1$$

$$\sigma_i \sigma_j = \sigma_j \sigma_i \text{ such that } |i - j| > 1$$

A unitary solution B of the braided Yang Baxter equation yields to a unitary representation ρ of the braided group B_n on the space $H^{\otimes n}$ for every n defined by

$$\rho(\sigma_i) = I^{\otimes i-1} \otimes B \otimes I^{\otimes n-i-1}$$

Moreover, this representation of braid group is unitary since R is also unitary operator, which indicate that this operator can performs topological entanglement and can be considers as quantum gate.

3 The R -matrices and quantum entanglement

First, we note that the usual definition of entangled states is given by defining separable pure states as decomposable tensor product and then declaring a state to be entangled if it is not separable. We give after some basic definitions :

Definition 4 *A qubit is a (normalized) state in the Hilbert space \mathbb{C}^2 . An n -qubit is a state in the tensor product Hilbert space $H = (\mathbb{C}^2)^{\otimes n} = \mathbb{C}^2 \otimes \dots \otimes \mathbb{C}^2$. The computational basis of H is the orthonormal basis given by the 2^n classical n -qubits*

$$|i_1 i_2 \dots i_n \rangle = |i_1 \rangle \otimes |i_2 \rangle \otimes \dots \otimes |i_n \rangle \quad (15)$$

where $0 \leq i_j \leq 1$. The general state in H is a superposition

$$|\psi \rangle = \sum \psi_{i_1 i_2 \dots i_n} |i_1 i_2 \dots i_n \rangle \quad (16)$$

where $\|\psi\|^2 = \sum |\psi_{i_1 i_2 \dots i_n}|^2 = 1$.

Definition 5 A quantum gate on n -qubits is a unitary operator $L : (\mathbb{C}^2)^{\otimes n} \rightarrow (\mathbb{C}^2)^{\otimes n}$. These gates form the unitary group $(\mathcal{U}^2)^{\otimes n} = \mathcal{U}(2^n)$. A sequence L_1, \dots, L_k of gates constitutes a quantum circuit on n -qubits.

Definition 6 A pure state $|\phi\rangle \in (H_1 \otimes H_2 \otimes \dots \otimes H_n)$ of a quantum system $(A_1 \otimes A_2 \otimes \dots \otimes A_n)$ is called *fully separable* with respect to the system $(A_1 \otimes A_2 \otimes \dots \otimes A_n)$ iff it can be written in the form

$$|\phi\rangle = |\phi_1\rangle \otimes |\phi_2\rangle \otimes \dots \otimes |\phi_n\rangle$$

where $|\phi_i\rangle$ is a pure state from H_i ; and $|\phi_i\rangle$ is called **entangled** with respect to the system $(A_1 \otimes A_2 \otimes \dots \otimes A_n)$ otherwise.

Definition 7 Let R be a unitary operator on $(H_1 \otimes H_2 \otimes \dots \otimes H_n)$ be a quantum gate for the composite system; R is called **entangling** if there exist a product state $|\phi_1, \phi_2, \dots, \phi_n\rangle$ such that the state $R(|\phi_1, \phi_2, \dots, \phi_n\rangle)$ is entangled.

More explicitly, if we denote the bases of a two dimensional vector space H over the Dirac notation $\{|0\rangle, |1\rangle\}$ and we give a general quantum state by the formulae:

$$|\psi\rangle = \sum_{\alpha} a_{\alpha} |\alpha\rangle$$

where α runs over all binary strings of length n . Thus we regard $|\psi\rangle$ as a general element of $H^{\otimes n}$ and we have the following theorem

Theorem 1 [16]

The state $|\psi\rangle = \sum_{\alpha} a_{\alpha} |\alpha\rangle$ is unentangled if and only if the following equations are satisfied for each coefficient in $|\psi\rangle$:

$$a_{0\dots 0}^{|\alpha|-1} a_{\alpha} = \prod_{i \in \alpha} a_{e_i}$$

With α a binary string as above, $|\alpha|$ denote the number of ones in the string, e_i denote the string of length n with all zeroes except for a 1 in the i -th place.

The simplest example of this theorem is the case of two entangled qubits. By the theorem,

$$|\psi\rangle = \alpha_{00}|00\rangle + \alpha_{01}|01\rangle + \alpha_{10}|10\rangle + \alpha_{11}|11\rangle \tag{17}$$

is unentangled exactly when

$$\alpha_{00}\alpha_{11} = \alpha_{10}\alpha_{01}$$

Consider now again the pure state $|\psi\rangle$ given in (17) written in a compact form by

$$|\psi\rangle = \sum_{i,j=0}^1 \alpha_{ij} |ij\rangle, \quad |ij\rangle = |i\rangle \otimes |j\rangle \tag{18}$$

and let S be an arbitrary Unitary R-Matrix satisfying the following relations:

$$S_{21} \cdot S = 1.$$

$$S_{12} \cdot S_{13} \cdot S_{23} = S_{23} \cdot S_{13} \cdot S_{12}$$

The R -matrix having the form

$$S = \begin{pmatrix} S_{00}^{00} & S_{01}^{00} & S_{10}^{00} & S_{11}^{00} \\ S_{00}^{01} & S_{01}^{01} & S_{10}^{01} & S_{11}^{01} \\ S_{00}^{10} & S_{01}^{10} & S_{10}^{10} & S_{11}^{10} \\ S_{00}^{11} & S_{01}^{11} & S_{10}^{11} & S_{11}^{11} \end{pmatrix}, \tag{19}$$

acts on the tensor product $|i\rangle \otimes |j\rangle$ as follows

$$\mathbf{S}|ij\rangle = \sum_{k=0}^1 \sum_{l=0}^1 \mathbf{S}_{ij}^{kl} |kl\rangle \quad (20)$$

where i, j, k, l take either 0 or 1. The Brylinski's theorem [55] says that it is a universal quantum gate when it is a quantum entangling operator which transforms a separable state $|\Phi_{ss}\rangle$ into an entangling state $\mathbf{S}|\Phi_{es}\rangle$ given by

$$\mathbf{S}|\Phi_{ss}\rangle = \sum_{i,j=0}^1 \sum_{k,l=0}^1 \mathbf{S}_{ij}^{kl} \alpha_{ij} |kl\rangle = \sum_{k,l=0}^1 d_{kl} |kl\rangle \quad (21)$$

where the coefficients α_{ij} satisfy $\alpha_{00}\alpha_{11} = \alpha_{01}\alpha_{10}$ and the coefficients d_{kl} are defined by

$$d_{kl} = \sum_{i,j=0}^1 \mathbf{S}_{ij}^{kl} \alpha_{ij} \quad (22)$$

satisfying $d_{00}d_{11} \neq d_{01}d_{10}$. If we introduce the 2×2 matrix A and the 2×2 matrix D as follows

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_{00} & \alpha_{01} \\ \alpha_{10} & \alpha_{11} \end{pmatrix}, \quad D = \begin{pmatrix} d_{00} & d_{01} \\ d_{10} & d_{11} \end{pmatrix} \quad (23)$$

The criteria of quantum entanglement for the quantum state determined by the matrix A (D) is that the determinant of the matrix A (D) is not zero, namely,

$$\alpha_{00}\alpha_{11} - \alpha_{01}\alpha_{10} = \text{Det}(A) \neq 0, \quad d_{00}d_{11} - d_{01}d_{10} = \text{Det}(D) \neq 0 \quad (24)$$

where the determinant $\text{Det}(A)$ (or $\text{Det}(D)$) can be called as the concurrence of the corresponding quantum state, see [56, 57]. In this work, in order to judge whether the unitary R -matrix is a universal quantum gate with the Brylinski's theorem [55], we choose $\text{Det}(A) = 0$ (so that the initial state is unentangled) and we prove that $\text{Det}(D) \neq 0$.

4 Quantum entangler based on a Star product on $SL(2)$ group

Let us now consider the particular case of Lie group $G = SL(2)$. We endow $SL(2)$ with a Poisson-Lie structure by defining a r -matrix \tilde{r} which verifies the classical YBE:

$$\tilde{r} = X_+ \otimes H - H \otimes X_+ \in \wedge^2 g$$

$$\text{where } X_+ = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \text{ and } H = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

So the corresponding Poisson bracket on $SL(2)$ has the following form:

$$\{\varphi, \psi\} = X_+^\ell(\varphi)H^\ell(\psi) - H^\ell(\varphi)X_+^\ell(\psi) - X_+^r(\varphi)H^r(\psi) + H^r(\varphi)X_+^r(\psi).$$

We consider the matrix $T = (t_{ij})_{i,j=1,2}$ of coordinate functions on $SL(2)$, i.e. the functions $t_{ij}(g) = g_{ij}$, where, for $g \in G$, we denote by g_{ij} its matrix elements.

Let us put:

$$T = \begin{pmatrix} t_{11} & t_{12} \\ t_{21} & t_{22} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix}.$$

Left and Right actions of G on matrix coordinates on G are given by:

$$\begin{aligned}
(X^\ell t_{ij})(g) &= (gX)_{ij} = \sum_k t_{ik}(g)X_{kj} \\
(X^r t_{ij})(g) &= (Xg)_{ij} = \sum_k X_{ik}t_{kj}(g)
\end{aligned} \tag{25}$$

with these notations, the Poisson bracket looks like:

$$\begin{aligned}
\{a, b\} &= 1 - a^2, \quad \{a, c\} = c^2, \quad \{b, c\} = c(a + d) \\
\{b, d\} &= d^2 - 1, \quad \{c, d\} = -c^2, \quad \{a, d\} = c(-a + d).
\end{aligned}$$

These relations define completely the Poisson-Lie group $SL(2)$ with r -matrix \tilde{r} since any $\varphi \in C^\infty(G)$ can be approximated by polynomial functions in a, b, c, d .

L. Takhtajan gives in [37] an elegant form of his star product defined in (5):

$$T_1 * T_2 = F^{-1}T \otimes TF \tag{26}$$

with

$$\begin{aligned}
T_1 &= T \otimes I \\
T_2 &= I \otimes T.
\end{aligned}$$

A star product for $SL(2)$ was given by Ohn in [58]

$$F = \exp\left[\frac{1}{2}\Delta_0(H) - \frac{1}{2}\left(H\frac{\sinh(hX_+)}{hX_+} \otimes e^{-hX_+} + e^{hX_+} \otimes H\frac{\sinh(hX_+)}{hX_+}\right)\frac{h\Delta_0(X_+)}{\sinh(h\Delta_0(X_+))}\right] \tag{27}$$

where Δ_0 is the usual comultiplication of the enveloping algebra.

The element $R_F = F_{21}^{-1}.F$ is a solution of algebraic Triangular quantum Yang Baxter equation:

$$(R_F)_{12}.(R_F)_{13}.(R_F)_{23} = (R_F)_{23}.(R_F)_{13}.(R_F)_{12}.$$

In the two-dimensional representation of the lie algebra $sl(2)$ defined above, R_F is presented by the R-matrix (denoted R) given by

$$R = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -h & h & h^2 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & -h \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & h \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \tag{28}$$

which satisfies the algebraic quantum Yang Baxter equation

$$(R)_{12}.(R)_{13}.(R)_{23} = (R)_{23}.(R)_{13}.(R)_{12}. \tag{29}$$

$$(R)_{21}.R = 1.$$

where $R_{12} = R \otimes I, R_{13} = (I \otimes P)(R \otimes I)(I \otimes P), R_{23} = I \otimes R$ and P denote the swap operator, where the swap permutation matrix P is the above 2-dimensional representation given by :

$$P = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}.$$

If we assume that $\{e_0, e_1\}$ is a basis of H over the Field \mathbb{C} and we denote the basis of the tensorial product $H \otimes H$ as $\{e_i \otimes e_j / i, j \in \{0, 1\}\}$. Using this basis we may describe the operator R by its action on the generators of $(H \otimes H)$

$$R(e_i \otimes e_j) = R_{ij}^{kl}(e_k \otimes e_l)$$

Particularly, the action of the operator R on the generators of $(H \otimes H)$ is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} R(e_1 \otimes e_1) &= (e_1 \otimes e_1) \\ R(e_1 \otimes e_2) &= -h(e_1 \otimes e_1) + (e_1 \otimes e_2) \\ R(e_2 \otimes e_1) &= h(e_1 \otimes e_1) + (e_2 \otimes e_1) \\ R(e_2 \otimes e_2) &= h^2(e_1 \otimes e_1) - h(e_1 \otimes e_2) + h(e_2 \otimes e_1) + (e_2 \otimes e_2) \end{aligned}$$

In the other side, the relations of the matrix element bialgebra $A(R)$ are obtained from the well-known FRT matrix relation,

$$RT_1T_2 = T_2T_1R$$

as

$$\begin{aligned} ca &= ac - hc^2, cd = dc - hc^2, \\ db &= bd + h(1 - d^2), \\ ab &= ba + h(1 - a^2), \\ cb &= bc - hac - hdc, \\ da &= ad + hac - hdc. \end{aligned}$$

Its not hard to see that R is a unitary solution of the algebraic quantum Yang Baxter equation :

$$R_{21} = PRP = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & h & -h & h^2 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & h \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & -h \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} = R^{-1}$$

Note that R is a unitary solution to the algebraic Yang-Baxter equation if and only if $B = RP$ given by :

$$B = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & h & -h & h^2 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & -h \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & h \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \tag{30}$$

is a solution to the quantum Yang-Baxter equation (braided Yang-Baxter equation)

$$(B \otimes I)(I \otimes B)(B \otimes I) = (I \otimes B)(B \otimes I)(I \otimes B) \tag{31}$$

Being triangular, i.e. $R_{21}R = I$, this R -matrix is trivially Hecke, with

$$(B - 1)(B + 1) = 0, \tag{32}$$

The matrix $B = RP$ has a spectral decomposition,

$$B = P^+ + P^-, \tag{33}$$

where $P^+ = \frac{1}{2}(B + I)$ is a rank 3 projector and $P^- = \frac{1}{2}(B - I)$ is a rank 1 projector. In the notation of Majid [59], these projectors provide the associated quantum co-plane, $A_{-1}^{2|0}$, and plane, $A_1^{2|0}$, respectively through the relations $P^\pm \mathbf{x}_1 \mathbf{x}_2 = 0$ where \mathbf{x} is the 2×1 column vector $\begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \end{pmatrix}$. These are associative algebras generated by the elements x and y subject to the relations,

$$y^2 = 0, \quad x^2 = -yx, \quad xy = -yx, \quad (34)$$

in the case of the co-plane $A_{-1}^{2|0}$, and,

$$xy = yx + hy^2 \quad (35)$$

in the case of the plane $A_1^{2|0}$.

From the point of view of braiding and algebra, we have the R -matrix B as a solution to the braided version of the Yang-Baxter equation, the R -matrix R is a solution to the algebraists version of the Yang- Baxter equation, and P is to be regarded as an algebraic permutation or as a representation of a virtual or flat crossing.

The main objective of this work, is to show explicitly that the universal R -matrix (solution of the algebraic quantum Yang Baxter equation) obtained from the quantization-deformation of a Poisson Lie group can be considered as quantum gate and can performs topological entanglement.

To do that, we consider the simplest pure states which occur when H_1 and H_2 are two dimensional with basis vectors $|0 \rangle$ and $|1 \rangle$ (Dirac notation).

The action of the R -Matrix R defined in (28) on the basis state $\{|00 \rangle, |01 \rangle, |10 \rangle, |11 \rangle\}$ of the tensor product $H_1 \otimes H_2$ give the following:

$$\begin{aligned} R|00 \rangle &= |00 \rangle, & R|11 \rangle &= h^2|00 \rangle - h|01 \rangle + h|10 \rangle + |11 \rangle \\ R|01 \rangle &= -h|00 \rangle + |01 \rangle, & R|10 \rangle &= h|00 \rangle + |10 \rangle \end{aligned}$$

In the same way, the action of the R -matrix $B = PR$ (solution of the braided Yang Baxter equation) is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} B|00 \rangle &= |00 \rangle, & B|11 \rangle &= h^2|00 \rangle - h|01 \rangle + h|10 \rangle + |11 \rangle \\ B|01 \rangle &= h|00 \rangle + |10 \rangle, & B|10 \rangle &= -h|00 \rangle + |01 \rangle \end{aligned}$$

Here is an elementary proof that the both operators R and B can entangle quantum states. In the general case, we choose the unentangled state $|\psi \rangle$ denoted by

$$|\psi \rangle = \sum_{i,j=0}^1 \alpha_{ij} |ij \rangle = \alpha_{00}|00 \rangle + \alpha_{01}|01 \rangle + \alpha_{10}|10 \rangle + \alpha_{11}|11 \rangle$$

with $\alpha_{00}\alpha_{11} = \alpha_{10}\alpha_{01}$. and we show that the states $|\phi \rangle = R(|\psi \rangle)$ and $|\Phi \rangle = B(|\psi \rangle)$ are entangled.

In fact, by direct computation we have :

$$\begin{aligned} |\phi \rangle &= R(|\psi \rangle) \\ &= R(\alpha_{00}|00 \rangle + \alpha_{01}|01 \rangle + \alpha_{10}|10 \rangle + \alpha_{11}|11 \rangle) \\ &= \alpha_{00}R(|00 \rangle) + \alpha_{01}R(|01 \rangle) + \alpha_{10}R(|10 \rangle) + \alpha_{11}R(|11 \rangle) \\ &= \alpha_{00}(|00 \rangle) + \alpha_{01}(-h|00 \rangle + |01 \rangle) + \alpha_{10}(h|00 \rangle + |10 \rangle) + \alpha_{11}(h^2|00 \rangle - h|01 \rangle + h|10 \rangle + |11 \rangle) \\ &= d_{00}|00 \rangle + d_{01}|01 \rangle + d_{10}|10 \rangle + d_{11}|11 \rangle. \end{aligned}$$

And the action of the matrix B is given by :

$$\begin{aligned} |\Phi \rangle &= B(|\psi \rangle) \\ &= B(\alpha_{00}|00 \rangle + \alpha_{01}|01 \rangle + \alpha_{10}|10 \rangle + \alpha_{11}|11 \rangle) \\ &= \alpha_{00}B(|00 \rangle) + \alpha_{01}B(|01 \rangle) + \alpha_{10}B(|10 \rangle) + \alpha_{11}B(|11 \rangle) \\ &= \alpha_{00}(|00 \rangle) + \alpha_{01}(h|00 \rangle + |10 \rangle) + \alpha_{10}(-h|00 \rangle + |01 \rangle) + \alpha_{11}(h^2|00 \rangle - h|01 \rangle + h|10 \rangle + |11 \rangle) \\ &= d'_{00}|00 \rangle + d'_{01}|01 \rangle + d'_{10}|10 \rangle + d'_{11}|11 \rangle \end{aligned}$$

where

$$d_{00} = \alpha_{00} - h\alpha_{01} + h\alpha_{10} + \alpha_{11}h^2; d_{01} = \alpha_{01} - h\alpha_{11}; d_{10} = \alpha_{10} + h\alpha_{11} \text{ and } d_{11} = \alpha_{11}$$

$$d'_{00} = \alpha_{00} - h\alpha_{01} + h\alpha_{10} + \alpha_{11}h^2; d'_{01} = \alpha_{10} - h\alpha_{11}; d'_{10} = \alpha_{01} + h\alpha_{11} \text{ and } d'_{11} = \alpha_{11}$$

The corresponding matrix 2×2 matrix D and 2×2 matrix D' are given by

$$D = \begin{pmatrix} d_{00} & d_{01} \\ d_{10} & d_{11} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_{00} - h\alpha_{01} + h\alpha_{10} + \alpha_{11}h^2 & \alpha_{01} - h\alpha_{11} \\ \alpha_{10} + h\alpha_{11} & \alpha_{11} \end{pmatrix}.$$

$$D' = \begin{pmatrix} d'_{00} & d'_{01} \\ d'_{10} & d'_{11} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_{00} + h\alpha_{01} - h\alpha_{10} + \alpha_{11}h^2 & \alpha_{10} - h\alpha_{11} \\ \alpha_{01} + h\alpha_{11} & \alpha_{11} \end{pmatrix}.$$

The determinants $Det(D)$ and $Det(D')$ are given by

$$Det(D) = 2h\alpha_{11}(\alpha_{10} - \alpha_{01}) + 2h^2\alpha_{11}^2$$

$$Det(D') = 2h\alpha_{11}(\alpha_{01} - \alpha_{10}) + 2h^2\alpha_{11}^2$$

which is not zero for the case of $\alpha_{11} \neq 0$. Hence the unitary R-matrix B and R are considered as quantum states entangler except for the unentangled states with $\alpha_{11} = 0$. Thus we can conclude (in view of definition (7)) that the states $|\phi \rangle = R(|\psi \rangle)$ and $|\Phi \rangle = B(|\psi \rangle)$ are entangled as a quantum states.

In the end it is important to note that the four orthonormal Bell states which have the forms,

$$|\psi_{\pm}\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|00\rangle \pm |11\rangle), \quad |\phi_{\pm}\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|10\rangle \pm |01\rangle). \quad (36)$$

Are transformed under the action of the quantum gates R and B as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} R|\psi_{\pm}\rangle &= |\psi_{\pm}^h\rangle \pm h|\phi_{-}\rangle & B|\psi_{\pm}\rangle &= |\psi_{\pm}^h\rangle \pm h|\phi_{-}\rangle \\ R|\phi_{-}\rangle &= |\phi_{-}\rangle + \frac{2h}{\sqrt{2}}|00\rangle & B|\phi_{-}\rangle &= -|\phi_{-}\rangle - \frac{2h}{\sqrt{2}}|00\rangle \\ R|\phi_{+}\rangle &= |\phi_{+}\rangle & B|\phi_{+}\rangle &= |\phi_{+}\rangle \end{aligned} \quad (37)$$

$$(38)$$

where $|\psi_{\pm}^h\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}((1 \pm h^2)|00\rangle \pm |11\rangle)$.

which implies that the entanglement is preserved under the action of the universal gates R and B .

References

- [1] A. Einstein, B. Podolsky, and N. Rosen, Can Quantum-Mechanical Description of Physical Reality be Considered Complete?, Phys. Rev. 47, 777-780 (1935).
- [2] J.S. Bell, On the Einstein-Podolsky-Rosen paradox, Physics 1 195-200 (1964).
- [3] R.F. Werner, Quantum States with Einstein-Podolsky-Rosen Correlations Admitting a Hidden-Variable Model, Phys. Rev. A 40 (1989) 4277.
- [4] Ryszard Horodecki, Pawe Horodecki, Micha Horodecki, and Karol Horodecki Quantum entanglement Rev. Mod. Phys. 81, 865 Published 17 June 2009
- [5] Nielsen, M. A. and Chuang, I. L., *Quantum Computation and Quantum Computation*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge (2000).

- [6] Bennett, C.H., Brassard, G., Crepeau, C., Jozsa, R., Peres, A. and Wootters, W. K., *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **70**, 1895–1899 (1993).
- [7] Shor, P. W.: Algorithms for Quantum Computation: Discrete Logarithms and Factoring. In S. Goldwasser, editor, Proceedings of the 35th Annual Symposium on the Foundations of Computer Science, pp. 124-134, Los Alamitos, CA, 1994. IEEE Computer Society Press.
- [8] Bennet, C. H. and Brassard, G., *Proceedings of IEEE International Conference on Computers, Systems Signal Processing, Bangalore, India*, IEEE, New York, p.175 (1984).
- [9] Ekert, A. K., *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **67**, 661–663 (1991).
- [10] R. Rausschendorf and H. Briegel, quant-ph/0010033.
- [11] D. Gottesman and I. Chuang, *Nature* 402 (1999) (6760) 390.
- [12] P. Rungta, V. Buzek, C.M. Caves, M. Hillery, and G.J. Milburn, *Phys. Rev. A* 64 (2001) 042315.
- [13] L. Kauffman and S. Lomonaco, *New J. Phys.* **4** (2002) 73.1–73.18.
- [14] L.H. Kauffman, *Quantum Computation and the Jones Polynomial*, in *Quantum Computation and Information*, S. Lomonaco, Jr. (ed.), AMS CONM/305, 2002, pp. 101–137.
- [15] L.H. Kauffman and S.J. Lomonaco Jr., *New J. Phys.* **4** (2002) 73.1–73.18.
- [16] L.H. Kauffman and S.J. Lomonaco Jr., *Entanglement Criteria–Quantum and Topological*, in *Quantum Information and Computation – Spie Proceedings, 21-22 April, 2003, Orlando, FL*, ed. by E. Donkor, A.R. Pirich and H.E. Brandt, Volume 5105, pp. 51–58.
- [17] L.H. Kauffman, *Quantum Topology and Quantum Computing*, in *Quantum Computation*, S. Lomonaco (ed.), AMS PSAPM/58, 2002, pp. 273–303.
- [18] L. H. Kauffman and S. J. Lomonaco Jr., *Quantum Knots*, in *Quantum Information and Computation II, Spie Proceedings, 12 -14 April 2004, Orlando, FL*, ed. by E. Donkor, A.R. Pirich and H.E. Brandt, Volume 5436, pp. 268-284.
- [19] L.H. Kauffman, *Opt. Spectrosc.* **9** (2005) 227-232. Arxiv: quan-ph/0407224.
- [20] L.H. Kauffman and S.J. Lomonaco Jr., *New J. Phys.* **6** (2004) 134. Arxiv: quant-ph/0401090.
- [21] Y. Zhang, L.H. Kauffman and M.L. Ge, *Universal Quantum Gate, Yang–Baxterization and Hamiltonian*; To appear in *Int. J. Quant. Inform.* **4** (2005), Arxiv: quant-ph/0412095.
- [22] H. Dye, *Quant. Inf. Proc.* **2** (2003) 117-150.
- [23] L.H. Kauffman, *Knots and Physics* (World Scientific Publishers, 2002).
- [24] P.K. Aravind, *Borromean Entanglement of the GHZ state*, in *Potentiality, Entanglement and Passion-at-a-Distance*, Cohen, Robert S., M. Horne, and J. Stachel (eds.), Kluwer Academic Publishers, Boston 1997.
- [25] H. Heydari, *J. Phys. A: Math. Theor.* **40** (2007) 9877 -9882.
- [26] H. Heydari, arXiv:0901.1269v1 [quant-ph] 9 Jan 2009.
- [27] H. Heydari, *J. Phys. A: Math. Gen.* **38** (2005) 11007-11017.
- [28] L.D Faddeev, *Integrables ;odeld in (1+1)dimensional quantum field theory*, lectures in Les Houches, 1982, Elsiever Science Publichers B.V.,1984

- [29] E. ABE, Cambridge tracts in math. no. 74, Cambridge University Press.
- [30] V. G. Drinfeld *Quantum groups* Proc. of the international congress of mathematicians, Berkeley, 1986, American Mathematical Society, 1987, 798
- [31] V. G. Drinfeld *Hopf algebras and the quantum Yang-Baxter equation* Sov. Math. Dokl. 32 (1985) 254
- [32] V. G. Drinfeld *A new realization of Yangians and quantized affine algebras* Sov. Math. Dokl. 36 (1988) 212
- [33] V. G. Drinfeld *Hamiltonian structures on Lie groups, Lie bi-algebras and the geometrical meaning of the classical Yang-Baxter equations* Sov. Math. Dokl. 27 (1983) 68
- [34] M. Jimbo *A q-difference analogue of $U(g)$ and the Yang-Baxter equation* Lett. Math. Phys. 10 (1985) 63
- [35] M. Jimbo *A q-analogue of $U(gl(N+1))$, Hecke algebra and the Yang-Baxter equation* Lett. Math. Phys. 10 (1986) 247
- [36] L.D Faddeev, N. Yu Reshetikhin, L.A Takhtajan, Algebra Analis 1, 178 1989
- [37] L. A. Takhtajan "Lectures on Quantum Groups" M. Ge and B. Zhao eds. World scientific (1989)
- [38] Bayen. F, Flato. M, Fronsdal. C, Lichnerowicz. A and Sternheimer. D, . Deformation theory and quantization, Ann. Phys 110,(1978) 111.
- [39] Bayen. F, Flato. M, Fronsdal. C, Lichnerowicz. A and Sternheimer. D, .Deformation theory and quantization, Ann. Phys 111,(1978) 61 .
- [40] Flato. M, Lichnerowicz. A and Sternheimer. D Compositio Mathematica 31, (1975) 41-82
- [41] Moreno. C and Valero. L, Star-products and quantization of Poisson-Lie groups, J. Geo. Phys. 9,(1992) 369-402
- [42] Moreno. C and Valero. L, Star-products and Quantum groups, in Physics on Manifolds, (1992) Kluwer, Dordrecht.
- [43] Moshe Flato and Daniel Sternheimer ,Topological Quantum Groups, Star Products and their relations, arXiv:hep-th/9409052v1
- [44] K. Akhouch, N. Belbara, F. Guedira and M. Mansour, Star Products and Topological Quantum Groups, Acta Physica Polonica B, vol. 32, Issue 4,p.1151
- [45] M. Mansour and K. Akhouch Star-products and Deformed Yangians Acta Physica Polonica B vol. 30 (1999) No 9.
- [46] Chari, V. and Pressley, A., *A Guide to Quantum Groups*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, (1994).
- [47] Majid, S., *Foundations of Quantum Group Theory*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge (1995).
- [48] Trindade, M. A. S. and Vianna, J D. M., *Physica A* **391**, 3413–3416 (2012).
- [49] Korbicz, J. K., Wehr, J., Lewenstein, M., *J. Math. Phys.* **50**, 062104 (2009).
- [50] Y. Zhang, N. Jing and M.L. Ge, Quantum Algebras Associated with Bell States. J.Phys. A: Math. Theor. 41 (2008) 055310.
- [51] J. Franko, E.C. Rowell and Z. Wang, Extraspecial 2-Groups and Images of Braid Group Representations. J. Knot Theory Ramifications, 15 (2006) 413-428.
- [52] Y. Zhang and M.L. Ge, GHZ States, Almost-Complex Structure and Yang Baxter Equation. Quant. Inf. Proc. vol. 6, no. 5, (2007) 363-379.

- [53] Y. Zhang, L.H. Kauffman and M.L. Ge, YangBaxterizations, Universal Quantum Gates and Hamiltonians. Quant. Inf. Proc. 4 (2005) 159-197. Arxiv: quant-ph/0502015.
- [54] V.G. Drinfeld (1983), on constant quasiclassical solutions of QYBE, Math. Dokhl. 28
- [55] J.L. Brylinski and R. Brylinski, Universal quantum gates, in *Mathematics of Quantum Computation*, Chapman & Hall/CRC Press, Boca Raton, Florida, 2002 (edited by R. Brylinski and G. Chen).
- [56] S. Hill and W.K. Wootters, Phys. Rev. Lett. **78** (1997) 5022-5025.
- [57] W.K. Wootters, Phys. Rev. Lett. **80** (1998) 2245-2248.
- [T] L. A Takhtajan. Lectures on Quantum Groups, M. Ge and B. Zhao eds. World scientific (1989).
- [58] C. Ohn, lectures in Math. Phys (1992), vol 25 Springer, Eerlin, pp. 85-88
- [59] S. Majid, *Foundations of Quantum Group Theory*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge (1995).